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3 1 Effects of nitrogen deposition on the abundance and metabolism of lichens:
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6 2 A meta-analysis
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3 21 **ABSTRACT**
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5 22 Lichens are the key to nutrient cycling and trophic networks in many terrestrial ecosystems
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8 23 and are good bioindicators of air pollution, including nitrogen (N) deposition.
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10 24 Experimental studies have shown that N deposition can reduce the abundance of lichens
11
12 25 and alter their thallus chemistry and metabolism, but we currently lack information about
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14 26 how widespread this effect is and what are the environmental factors modulating the
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16 27 response of lichens to N. We carried out a meta-analysis of the literature about the effects
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18 28 of experimental N fertilization on lichen abundance and metabolism. We found thirty-
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20 29 nine articles from thirty-one experimental sites that met our search criteria. These studies
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22 30 showed that the addition of N accelerates lichen metabolism in the short term and
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24 31 decreases their abundance in the medium-long term. Early senescence of lichens is
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26 32 proposed as a possible mechanism linking the two observed responses. Chlorolichens
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28 33 from regions with high precipitation (> 1000 mm) and with a background N deposition of
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30 34 mixed origin (agricultural and industrial) were the most affected by N, in terms of both
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32 35 abundance and metabolism. Structural equation modelling showed that the rate of N
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34 36 addition was the main factor in modulating the response of lichens to N in terms of
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36 37 metabolism, whereas isothermality played a very important role in modulating the lichen
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38 38 response to N in terms of abundance. Our meta-analysis identified that excess N
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40 39 deposition reduces lichen abundance and increases the metabolism of sensitive species,
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42 40 especially across European ecosystems; lichens from more climatically benign regions
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44 41 (i.e., greater precipitation and isothermality) are the most affected.
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55 43 **Keywords:** Global change; Lichens; Meta-analysis; Nitrogen deposition; Nitrogen
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57 44 fertilization; Structural equations models (SEM).
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45 **Highlights**

- 46 • The addition of N accelerates lichen metabolism in the short-term
- 47 • The addition of N decreases lichen abundance in the medium-long term
- 48 • Isothermality modulated the lichen response in terms of abundance

50 **INTRODUCTION**

51 Lichens are a key to nutrient cycling in many terrestrial ecosystems, where they fix
52 atmospheric carbon (C) and, in the case of cyanolichens, non-reactive nitrogen (N) in
53 association with diazotrophic cyanobacteria (Nash 2008; Asplund and Wardle 2016).
54 Lichens are also key elements of trophic networks in many ecosystems (Asplund and
55 others 2010; Bokhorst and others 2015; Asplund and Wardle 2016), where they can play
56 a very important role in the stabilization of soils, allowing a greater retention of reactive
57 N (Asplund and Wardle 2016). Together with their important role in the biogeochemical
58 cycling of N, lichens are very good bioindicators of air pollution (Conti and Cecchetti
59 2001; Holt and Miller 2011). Lichens are very sensitive to factors like acid rain and N
60 deposition (Ochoa-Hueso and others 2014a; Pinho and others 2014) because they are: (1)
61 able to absorb nutrients and pollutants over their entire surface; (2) abundant and common
62 in many ecosystems, with many species having cosmopolitan or subcosmopolitan
63 distributions; and (3) comparatively well studied in pollution research. Moreover, lichens
64 are used as bioindicators of N deposition in two different ways: (1) thallus N content of
65 tolerant lichen species as a cheaper alternative to instrument monitoring; and (2) shifts in
66 lichen community composition and abundance, plus metabolic studies on sensitive
67 species. Although lichens are frequently used as model organisms in studies about spatio-
68 temporal patterns of atmospheric N deposition (Sheppard and others 2011), we lack a
69 clear understanding of the environmental conditions (e.g., climate, soil type, vegetation

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3 70 type) modulating the response of lichens to N deposition at a global scale, both in terms
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5 71 of abundance and metabolism.
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8 72 Nitrogen deposition is caused by fossil fuel burning (typically linked to oxidized
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10 73 N deposition), and livestock and agricultural activities (typically linked to deposition of
11
12 74 reduced N), and is the third main cause of global biodiversity loss (Bobbink and others
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14 75 1998, 2010; Sala and others 2000). Currently, the world average rate of anthropogenic N
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16 76 deposition is ~10 kg N/ha/year above of ambient levels (~1 kg N/ha/year) (Galloway and
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18 77 others 2008), and this rate could double by 2050 and even reach 50 kg N/ha/year in certain
19
20 78 regions (Galloway and others 2004). An occasional increase in N deposition does not
21
22 79 usually cause lethal effects on lichens, which are capable of tolerating experimental
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24 80 additions of up to 50 kg N/ha/year, at least in the short term (for example, Johansson and others
25
26 81 2012). In contrast, chronic N deposition typically (1) decreases lichen abundance (Ochoa-
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28 82 Hueso and others 2017; Varela Río and others 2017); (2) increases thallus N, as well as
29
30 83 the concentration of photosynthetic and/or photoprotective pigments (Root and others
31
32 84 2013; Ochoa-Hueso and others 2014b); (3) decreases N fixation in cyanolichens (Varela
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34 85 Río and others 2017); (4) reduces lichen photosynthetic rate (Varela Río and others
35
36 86 2017); and (5) alters the structure and composition of lichen communities, which often
37
38 87 implies a reduction in species richness (Wolseley and others 2006; Davies and others
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40 88 2007; Johansson and others 2012; Reed and others 2016; Ochoa-Hueso and others 2017).
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42 89 Despite the consensus in the dominant type of sensitive lichen response to N deposition,
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44 90 synthesizing the available results from realistic experimental studies of N pollution (that is,
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46 91 N addition experiments under field conditions) on lichen abundance and metabolism will
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48 92 be extremely useful to more effectively develop biomonitoring programs based on a
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50 93 priori knowledge derived from experimental field research.
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3 94 The ability of lichens to reflect atmospheric N deposition can be modulated by
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5 95 local climatic conditions, soil type (in the case of terrestrial lichens), and the dominant
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7 96 vegetation type (Bobbink and others 2010), which may explain the great variability of
8
9 97 lichen response that is typically reported across species and sites. For example, greater
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11 98 soil N content and more mesic conditions could be linked with more pronounced lichen
12
13 99 responses to N deposition, given that lichens are exposed to greater N concentration and
14
15 100 are active for longer periods (Hauck 2010; Ochoa-Hueso and others 2017). In this sense,
16
17 101 isothermality (defined as mean diurnal range/temperature annual range), which is an
18
19 102 important driver of lichen richness at the global scale (Coyle and Hurlbert 2016), could
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21 103 play a key role. Similarly, the presence of a well-developed canopy of woody plants, such
22
23 104 as in forests, woodlands and dense shrublands, may buffer against the negative effects of
24
25 105 increased N deposition by retaining and recycling an important proportion of N entering
26
27 106 the system. In contrast, greater plant production and accumulation of standing biomass in
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29 107 more open ecosystems, such as grasslands and open shrublands, may result in more
30
31 108 negative effects of N on lichens due to more direct exposure and as these lichens are not
32
33 109 able to effectively compete with grasses for the available space (Lee and Caporn 2000).
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35 110 Regarding the role of soils, terrestrial lichens growing on acidic, and thus less buffered,
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37 111 soils, may be more negatively affected by increased N due to both the direct effects of
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39 112 extra N and the indirect effects associated with the decrease of soil pH, reduced base
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41 113 cation availability, and the solubilization of toxic metals (Horswill and others 2008;
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43 114 Stevens and others 2010; Ochoa-Hueso and others 2017). Understanding how
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45 115 environmental conditions modulate the way in which lichens respond to N will also be a
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47 116 key to refining biomonitoring studies using lichens from natural environments, making
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49 117 our study both timely and relevant.
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3 118 In this study, we performed a meta-analysis of the effects of experimental N
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5 119 fertilization on lichen abundance and metabolism, and assessed the importance of both
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7 120 environmental variables (climate, soil properties and vegetation type) and procedural
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9 121 variables (N dose and form and experimental duration) as modulators of the lichen
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11 122 response to N. Given that most of the studies considered in this meta-analysis concern N-
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13 123 sensitive species (Table 1), we predicted that experimental N addition would consistently
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15 124 reduce the lichen abundance (Johansson and others 2012) and accelerate their metabolism
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17 125 (Root and others 2013) across regions. We also predicted that the magnitude of lichen
18
19 126 abundance response to N addition would be proportional to the N load added and to the
20
21 127 duration of the experiment. In addition, we hypothesized that the effects generated by
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23 128 additions of reduced N would be more negative than those exerted by additions of
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25 129 oxidized N due to the toxic effect of this form in high concentrations (Hauck 2010; Varela
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27 130 Río and others 2017). Given the determinant role of isothermality (defined as mean
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29 131 diurnal range/temperature annual range, and interpreted as a measure of climate
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31 132 stability/benignity) on lichen richness at global scale (Coyle and Hurlbert 2016), we
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33 133 predicted that lichen response to N deposition would be strongly conditioned by this
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35 134 variable, and that the modulating effect of isothermality would be greater than that of other
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37 135 climatic variables of more widespread use in global studies, such as mean annual
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39 136 precipitation, or temperature. Finally, we hypothesized that the presence of woody
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41 137 vegetation (shrublands and, particularly, forests) would buffer against the negative the
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43 138 effects of N fertilization on lichen abundance seen in more open habitats.
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139 MATERIAL AND METHODS

140 *Data collection*

141 We used *Scopus* to search for studies that contained the following combination of words:
142 “*lichen & nitrogen deposition*”, “*lichen & nitrogen addition*”, “*lichen & nitrogen*
143 *fertilization*”. We completed the search with additional studies obtained from references
144 contained in the articles from the initial search. Last search was carried out on August 1,
145 2019. We then built a database with the response of lichens to N addition concerning
146 variables related to their abundance and metabolism. The criteria used for the selection of
147 the studies were: (1) studies should involve experimental N fertilization in terrestrial
148 ecosystems; (2) the variables examined should be the abundance of lichens (essentially
149 cover, but also biomass and growth measurements; Table 1; Appendix 1) or various
150 metrics related to metabolism (e.g., thallus N concentration, photosynthetic efficiency,
151 etc.; Table 1); (3) when several sets of data were available from the same experimental
152 site (be it in several publications or within a single one), only the latest set was used to
153 preserve the assumption of independence of observations. For each article, we obtained
154 information about the type of fertilizer used, the dose applied, and the duration of the
155 experiment (Table 1). When the numeric values of means and measures of variance were
156 not given directly, and only figures were presented, we used the *GetData Graph Digitizer*
157 program (<http://www.getdata-graph-digitizer.com/>) and the *Digitize* package in R version
158 3.6.1 (R Core Team 2019), which allow a reliable estimation of these numerical data from
159 their graphic representation.

160 We also obtained data on relevant bioclimatic variables from *WorldClim* (Hijmans
161 and others 2005), including average annual precipitation (MAP), average annual
162 temperature (MAT]) and isothermality (ISOT). Besides, we extracted N deposition
163 estimates (total, oxidized and reduced) for each location based on Dentener and others

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3 164 (2006) (Fig. 1). The global map obtained is generated using a three-dimensional global
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5 165 model with data on chemical transport, estimated emissions and climatic scenarios, based
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7 166 on real deposition data obtained in 1993 (Dentener and others 2006). The size of each cell
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9 167 of the model is 5° in longitude (~ 555 km at the equator) by 3.75° in latitude (~ 407 km).
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11 168 Although this large cell size, along with the difference in dates between our data and those
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13 169 used by the model, limits the accuracy of its application to a given site, the patterns
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15 170 provided by this model have been shown to remain consistent and directly comparable
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17 171 with the current N deposition global patterns (Stevens and others 2015). When possible,
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19 172 we also extracted data about soil parameters (soil fertility [C and N content] and pH) for
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21 173 each location. This information was obtained from the same studies considered in the
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23 174 meta-analysis or from other studies carried out at the same location.
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29 175 To examine how climatic variables, the characteristics of the treatment, soil
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31 176 variables, the background N deposition, and the type of ecosystem affect the response of
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33 177 lichens to N deposition, we categorized the studies according to their: (1) dominant
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35 178 vegetation type (shrub, forest and grassland); (2) degree of isothermality (ISOT),
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37 179 understood as the ratio between the mean of the daily temperature range and the annual
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39 180 temperature range ($\leq 25\%$ and $> 25\%$); (3) mean annual precipitation (MAP; < 600 ; ≥ 600
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41 181 and < 1000 ; ≥ 1000 mm/year); (4) experimental dose (≤ 12 ; $> 12 \times \leq 36$; > 36 kg N/ha/year);
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43 182 (5) experimental duration (≤ 12 ; $> 12 \times \leq 36$; > 36 months); (6) main origin of the
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45 183 background N deposition (agricultural, industrial, or mixed), understood as the ratio
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47 184 between the background deposition of reduced and oxidized N (< 0.75 ; $\geq 0.75 \times \leq 1.25$;
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49 185 $s > 1.25$); and (7) pH (acidic-neutral, ≤ 6 ; to neutral-basic, > 6). These categorizations were
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51 186 based on response expectations and data availability. In addition, in the case of the
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53 187 response variables related to the metabolism of lichens, we classified them according to
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55 188 whether they were related to: (1) photosynthesis (activity of photosystems and the
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3 189 RubisCO enzyme, and maximum quantum efficiency, [FvFm]); (2) pigments
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5 190 (concentration of chlorophylls, carotenoids, etc.); (3) secondary metabolites (for example, usnic
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7 191 acid, norstictic acid, and so on); (4) thallus N concentration (all the lichens considered in this
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9 192 study on which thallus N was measured are N-sensitive species, which justifies thallus N
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11 193 as a metabolic response; this sensitivity was based on the abundance response of those
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13 194 lichens at the experimental sites or on previous literature; Ochoa-Hueso and Gutierrez-
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15 195 Larruga (2019), Table 1 and Appendix 1); (5) other nutrients and cellular compounds
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17 196 (including concentration of soluble sugars and proteins, phosphorus, potassium, sulfur
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19 197 and calcium; these were not separately analyzed due to lack of enough data); (6) enzyme
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21 198 activity (related to nutrient acquisition and stress response) and; (7) fungal biomass
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23 199 (chitin and ergosterol).

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29 200 *Statistical analysis*

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32 201 *Meta-analysis*

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35 202 The meta-analysis was carried out according Hedges *et al.* (1999). The effect size
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37 203 associated with the treatment effect for each observation was estimated as the natural
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39 204 logarithm of the response ratio ($\ln RR$) [1].

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$$\ln RR = \ln\left(\frac{\bar{X}_t}{\bar{X}_c}\right) = \ln \bar{X}_t - \ln \bar{X}_c \quad [1]$$

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45 206 Where \bar{X}_t represents the treatment mean and \bar{X}_c the mean of the control. A value of zero
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47 207 indicates that there is no change in the response variable due to N fertilization, while a
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49 208 positive or negative value represents an increase or decrease in the response variable. The
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51 209 use of the logarithm linearizes the measurement of the response ratio and provides a more
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53 210 normal distribution for small sample sizes. In addition, the variance of the $\ln RR$ was
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55 211 calculated according to the equation [2].
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$$\hat{\mathcal{V}}_{\ln RR} = \left(\frac{s_t^2}{n_t \bar{X}_t^2} \right) + \left(\frac{s_c^2}{\bar{X}_c^2} \right) \quad [2]$$

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7 213 Where s_t y s_c are the standard deviation of the treatment and control, respectively; and n_t
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9 214 y n_c the sample size of the treatment and control respectively.
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13 215 We only considered one observation per experimental site and N addition level.
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15 216 Thus, in those studies that report results from several species, metabolic variables and N
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17 217 forms, we averaged effect sizes and standard errors across species, traits and N forms.
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19 218 The separate effects of these categories were subsequently tested by sub-setting the
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21 219 original dataset. In order to consider the variability both within each study and between
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23 220 different studies, a random effects meta-analysis model was used. Statistical analyses
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25 221 were carried out using the 'metacont' function of the *meta*-package (Schwarzer 2007) in
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27 222 R. The analyses were separately done for "abundance", "metabolism", and all the
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29 223 environmental and metabolic categories previously described.
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33 224 *Ecological models*

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36 225 We used structural equation modelling (SEM) (Grace 2006; Eisenhauer and others 2015)
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38 226 to evaluate the causality of the modulating role of a series of environmental and
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40 227 procedural variables on the size of the response of lichens, both in terms of abundance
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42 228 and metabolism (i.e., all metabolic variables pooled together). This method allows to
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44 229 account for both the direct and indirect effects that different variables may have on the
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46 230 response variable. We followed a d-sep approach using the *piecewiseSEM* package
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48 231 (version 2.0.2) in R, in which a set of linear structured equations are evaluated
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50 232 individually. This approach allows us to account for nested experimental designs. To run
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52 233 the linear mixed models, we used the 'lme' function of the *nlme* package, including
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54 234 experimental site as a random factor. Good fit was assumed when Fisher's C values were
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56 235 non-significant ($p > 0.05$). We built a total of six models, three for abundance and three
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3 236 for metabolism, depending on the nature of the background N deposition (that is, total,
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5 237 reduced or oxidized). In the case of abundance models, the sample size was 62, while for
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7 238 the metabolism it was 25. The sample size of abundance models was greater than that
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9 239 used in the meta-analyses (53) due to the lack of variance measures for some data that
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11 240 could, therefore, not be used for the meta-analysis but that are usable for SEMs. Prior to
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13 241 model design, "exploratory" nonparametric Spearman rank correlations were carried out between
14
15 242 lichen abundance and metabolism and all the independent variables considered. We used
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17 243 Spearman correlations because they show a broader range of potential relationships in
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19 244 exploratory analyses. In our a priori model, depicted based on the existing literature and
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21 245 the information obtained from the Spearman correlations (Supplementary Tables 1 and
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23 246 2), the lnRR was predicted to be directly affected by N addition rate, experimental
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25 247 duration, latitude, isothermality, background N deposition. In addition, latitude was
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27 248 predicted to directly affect the lnRR, isothermality and background N deposition, while
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29 249 isothermality was predicted to affect background N deposition. To account for the
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31 250 modulating effect of isothermality and background N deposition on lnRR, we included
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33 251 their interactions with experimental duration and N load added, respectively.
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44 252 **RESULTS**

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46 254 We found thirty-nine articles that met our criteria, totaling thirty-one experimental sites
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48 255 (Table 1, Figure 1; experimental designs are detailed in Appendix 1). All the experimental
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50 256 sites are in the northern hemisphere, and most of them (twenty-five out of thirty-one) in
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52 257 Europe, with Sweden being the most represented country. Approximately 60% of the
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54 258 studies were published in the last 15 years. Most of the studies reported lichen cover.
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56 259 Regarding the characteristics of the lichens considered in the publications, almost all were
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3 260 terricolous lichens. Few experiments studied the entire lichen community, and the
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5 261 majority considered chlorolichens only. The most used fertilizer was ammonium nitrate
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7 262 (NH_4NO_3) with doses ranging from low (2.5 kg N/ha/year) to very high (600 kg
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9 263 N/ha/year), although most experiments used intermediate doses (between 10 and 56 kg
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11 264 N/ha/year).

15 265 *Meta-analysis*

18 266 *ABUNDANCE*

21 267 The abundance of lichens (Figure 2a) widely decreased with N fertilization ($\ln\text{RR} = -1.0158$,
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23 268 $p < 0.0001$). Both terricolous and epiphytic lichens with green algae as photobiont (i.e.,
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25 269 chlorolichens) were the most negatively affected ($\ln\text{RR} = -1.0554$, $p < 0.0001$), although
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27 270 this could be due to the low number of observations involving cyanolichens ($n = 3$). We
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29 271 also found particularly negative effects of N on lichens growing in shrublands ($\ln\text{RR} = -$
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31 272 1.4895 , $p < 0.0001$) and in locations with an annual precipitation greater than 1000 mm
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33 273 ($\ln\text{RR} = -1.3914$, $p = 0.0372$). In addition, lichens growing on acidic substrates (i.e., pH
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35 274 less 6; $\ln\text{RR} = -1.2218$, $p < 0.0001$) and in locations where background N deposition is of
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37 275 mixed ($\ln\text{RR} = -1.8083$, $p < 0.0001$) and industrial origin ($\ln\text{RR} = -0.3959$, $p < 0.0001$)
38
39 276 were more negatively affected by N.

44 277 Significant effects of N addition only emerged after long-term fertilization (>36
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46 278 months; $\ln\text{RR} = -1.2755$, $p < 0.0001$), and with N loads higher than 10 kg N/ha/yr.

49 279 Fertilization with ammonium nitrate had a significant negative effect on the abundance
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51 280 of lichens ($\ln\text{RR} = -0.9199$, $p < 0.0001$).

54 281 *METABOLISM*

57 282 Nitrogen addition consistently accelerated the metabolism of lichens, as evidenced by a
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59 283 consistent greater response of metabolic parameters under increased N ($\ln\text{RR} = 0.2844$, p

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3 284 < 0.0001; Figure 2b). Thallus N content (lnRR = 0.2903, $p < 0.0001$), pigment content (lnRR
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5 285 = 0.3438, $p = 0.0010$) and enzyme activity (lnRR = 0.2696, $p = 0.0004$) were the variables
6
7 286 that showed stronger responses. Similar to what we observed for the abundance-related
8
9 287 variables, terricolous and epiphytic lichens with green algae as photobiont (i.e.,
10 288 chlorolichens) showed the greatest response to N (lnRR = 0.3457, $p < 0.0001$). We found
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12 289 a greater positive effect in grasslands (lnRR = 0.6595, $p = 0.0055$) and where annual
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14 290 rainfall ranges between 600 and 1000 mm (lnRR = 0.4622, $p < 0.0001$). In addition,
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16 291 lichens growing on acidic substrates (pH less than or equal to 6; lnRR = 0.4622, $p <$
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18 292 0.0001) and in locations where background N deposition is of mixed (lnRR = 0.3874, $p <$
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20 293 0.0001) and industrial origin (lnRR = 0.3884, $p = 0.0616$) were more affected by N.

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22 294 For metabolism-related variables, significant effects of N addition emerged short
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24 295 after the start of fertilization (< 12 months; lnRR = 0.2981, $p = 0.0009$) and remained over
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26 296 time. The addition of ammonium resulted in the clearest effects (lnRR = 0.4827, $p <$
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28 297 0.0001).

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30 298 *Structural evaluation models: integrating N deposition effects and*
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32 299 *environmental and procedural variables*

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34 300 The SEMs related to abundance (Figure 3a-c) showed that all the variables selected
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36 301 have a negative effect on lnRR. The greater the amount of N added and for longer periods
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38 302 of time, the lower the lichen abundance (Figure 3a-c; Supplementary Figure 1). We
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40 303 also observed that as the background N deposition increased, the abundance of lichens
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42 304 decreased, with similar effect size for total (Figure 3a), reduced (Figure 3b) and oxidized
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44 305 deposition (Figure 3c). Isothermality had a weak negative effect on lnRR, but was important
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46 306 modulating the effect of experimental duration, whereby lichens from sites with greater
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48 307 isothermality showed a more pronounced response to N over time (Figure 3a-c).

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3 308 Moreover, lichens from experimental sites with receiving greater background N
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5 309 deposition responded more negatively to increasing N doses.
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8 310 Lichen metabolism was mostly explained by experimental N load and total
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10 311 background N deposition, while the rest of variables and interactions considered did not
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12 312 seem to play a role in their response (Figure 3d-f). We also found a positive
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14 313 relationship between lnRR and soil N ($\rho = 0.8466$, $p = 0.0010$; Supplementary Table
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16 314 2). Figures 4 and 5 show partial correlations between predictors and lnRR for both
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18 315 metabolism and abundance models, demonstrating that, when they occur, the
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20 316 relationships between variables were predominantly linear.
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26 317 **DISCUSSION**

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28 318 In this study, we have shown that N deposition can have widespread long-term
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30 319 detrimental effects on lichen abundance, possibly due to a sustained accelerated metabolic
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32 320 activity. This may, in turn, lead to a faster senescence of lichens. The acceleration of
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34 321 metabolism was most clearly manifested as an increase in the concentration of thallus N
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36 322 and chlorophylls and a greater enzymatic activity. The most sensitive lichens were those
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38 323 from shrublands exposed to higher precipitation and with more stable and benign climatic
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40 324 conditions, while the most evident responses occurred under long-term fertilization with
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42 325 N doses higher than 10 kg N/ha/yr.
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47 326 The type of symbiont may determine the way in which lichens respond to N
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49 327 addition. Cyanolichens may have a competitive advantage in low-nutrient environments
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51 328 due to their cyanobacterial symbionts and their ability to fix atmospheric N, which is why
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53 329 they are typically assumed to be more sensitive to high N loads (Fenn and others 2003).
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55 330 However, our results do not show significant responses for cyanolichens and the greatest
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57 331 effects were observed in chlorolichens. We hypothesize that the fact that cyanolichens
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3 332 accumulate N from N fixation is masking the effects of N addition. However, the scarce
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5 333 number of studies focused on cyanolichens hampers the assessment of these results.
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8 334 Environmental variables are known to play a very important role in the modulation
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10 335 of the response of lichens to N addition (Bobbink and others 2010; Ochoa-Hueso and
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12 336 others 2017). For example, the accumulation of inorganic N (NO_3^- , NH_4^+) promoted by
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14 337 unfavorable, drought-related factors, such as higher temperatures and lower precipitation,
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16 338 may cause the disappearance of lichen communities (Delgado-Baquerizo and others
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18 339 2014; Varela Río and others 2017). However, our results show that the negative response
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20 340 of lichens to N addition is greater when the environmental conditions are more favorable
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22 341 for lichen activity and growth, as evidence by the negative effect of greater isothermality
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24 342 and annual precipitation. This is probably due to the longer active periods of the lichens,
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26 343 which would increase their vulnerability to N. In contrast, adverse temperature and
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28 344 humidity conditions would render them inactive, thus gaining protection against the stress
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30 345 caused by N (Varela Río and others 2017), at least in the short-term. Conversely, we
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32 346 hypothesize that greater metabolic activity under more favorable conditions coupled with
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34 347 the metabolic acceleration promoted by the extra N may result in that lichen thalli could
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36 348 die earlier due to premature senescence and, consequently, affect negatively their
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38 349 abundance. This result is in agreement with the role of isothermality, interpreted as an
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40 350 indicator of climatic stability/benignity, in the distribution of lichens at global scale, even
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42 351 more than other climatic variables such as MAP and MAT (Coyle and Hurlbert 2016).
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44 352 However, the lower variance explained by the abundance models and the relationship
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46 353 between $\ln RR$ and latitude in the case of the model with oxidized background N
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48 354 deposition also suggests that there may be other environmental variables, apart from
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50 355 isothermality, that we have not considered in our models and that may be modulating the
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52 356 response of lichens to N fertilization. These variables could include, for instance, soil
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3 357 organic matter content, which varies positively with latitude in the Northern Hemisphere
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5 358 (Plaza and others 2018).
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8 359 In addition to the modulating role of climatic conditions, we hypothesized that the
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10 360 presence of woody vegetation may buffer against the effects of N deposition on lichens
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12 361 by taking up some of that N that will therefore not reach the lichen thallus. In the case of
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14 362 the variables related to metabolism, there was a gradient in the magnitude of the effects
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16 363 from the forest to the grassland. Therefore, the effect that the addition of N has on the
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18 364 metabolism of lichens could indeed be buffered by the presence of woody plants. This
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20 365 may be due to the fact that forest, and to a lesser extent shrubland, canopies intercept
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22 366 pollutants and/or are able to build up a complex network of fungal hyphae that would
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24 367 retranslocate nutrients away from the lichens more efficiently (Ochoa-Hueso and others
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26 368 2018). In contrast, lichens from shrublands were those that were more negatively and
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28 369 significantly affected by N deposition (Lee and Caporn 2000; Barker 2001; Bobbink and
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30 370 others 2010). Taken together, these results suggest that the presence of a woody canopy
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32 371 interacts with the way in which N reaches the lichens, but also that this does not
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34 372 necessarily translates to less effects, which may point to contrasting mechanisms through
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36 373 which the damage occur in different habitats. However, the sample size available limits
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38 374 our ability to make broad generalizations.
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45 375 The effects caused by N deposition on lichens are more pronounced when N is
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47 376 chronically added as high loads of a combination of reduced and oxidized N compounds
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49 377 (NO_3^- and NH_4^+), which is agreement with the more negative effects observed in sites
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51 378 receiving N deposition from mixed origin. Moreover, many studies suggest a response of
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53 379 ecosystems proportional to the N load applied, as well as to the duration of treatment.
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55 380 However, our results show that in lichens this response is particularly clear for those
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57 381 variables related to metabolism, but not for those regarding abundance; our abundance
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3 382 metric also showed that the abundance of lichens is only consistently impacted in
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5 383 experiments that use doses higher than 10 kg N/ha/year. These results show that lichens
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7 384 are able to tolerate N deposition values lower than 10 kg N/ha/year, at least in the short
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9 385 term (Johansson and others 2012; Varela Río and others 2017), but that chronic deposition
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11 386 will invariably reduce their abundance.
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16 387 **CONCLUSIONS**

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18 388 Our study suggests that N addition causes an early acceleration of lichen metabolism
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20 389 (mostly attributed to thallus N and pigment accumulation and greater enzyme activity),
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22 390 that could explain a parallel decrease in their abundance in the long-term. For both
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24 391 abundance and metabolism, chlorolichens showed the greatest response, particularly in
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26 392 wetter regions with greater isothermality and with a background deposition of mixed
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28 393 origin. Lichens from grasslands were the most affected in terms of metabolism,
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30 394 suggesting that the presence of woody vegetation can interact with way through which N
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32 395 affects the lichens. Our SEMs also showed that isothermality modulated the effect of N
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34 396 on lichen abundance, indicating that lichens exposed to more stable conditions throughout
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36 397 the year are more likely to be negatively impacted by N deposition over time. In the case
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38 398 of metabolism, the N load applied was the main driver of lichen response, suggesting the
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40 399 general applicability of physiological/metabolic responses as bioindicators of N pollution.
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42 400 The role of procedural variables (i.e., N load and form and experimental duration) also
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44 401 indicates that the way in which each individual experiment is performed will at least
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46 402 partially influence the findings of the study, calling for the harmonization of experiments
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48 403 in future studies evaluating the effects of N deposition on lichens (e.g., through the
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50 404 development of coordinated networks). The wider generalization of our study is also
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52 405 limited by the amount of experiments published and the skewed geographic distribution
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54 406 of study sites, making our study mostly applicable to European ecosystems. We,
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3 407 therefore, recommend caution when interpreting our analysis at the global scale.
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5 408 Acknowledging these limitations, our results do suggest that N deposition effects on
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7 409 lichen abundance and metabolism are widespread and that climatic changes (e.g., changes
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9 410 in precipitations and isothermality due to the greater incidence of extreme events) will
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11 411 affect the way in which lichens respond to N. This will alter the supply of ecosystem
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13 412 services provided by lichens such as soil stabilization, participation in food webs and/or
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15 413 the biogeochemical cycling of N and C.
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21
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640 **Table 1.** Summary of the thirty-nine articles used in the meta-analysis.

Article	Article Number	Country/Region	Ecosystem type	Metabolic variable evaluated	Abundance	Background N deposition (kg/ha/year)*	Ecotype	Symbiosis	N fertilization		
									Fertilizer load (kg/ha/year)	Experimental duration (months)	Fertilizer type
Bähring and others 2017	1	Germany	Shrubland		x	18.14	1	1	2.5	30	NH ₄ NO ₃
Benner and Vitousek, 2007	2	Hawaii	Forest		x	0.34	2	2	100	12	CH ₄ N ₂ O + NH ₄ NO ₃
Britton and Fisher, 2007	3	Scotland	Shrubland		x	4.53	1	1	10/20/50	58	NH ₄ NO ₃
Carroll and others, 1999	4	Wales	Shrubland		x	12.29	1	1	40/80/120	108	NH ₄ NO ₃
Dahlman and others, 2002	5	Sweden	Forest	2, 4, 7 ^a	x	1.84	1	2	5	3	NH ₄ NO ₃ , NH ₄ CL, KNO ₃
Eriksson and Raunistola, 1993	6	Sweden	Forest		x	1.48	1	1	150/250	132	NH ₄ NO ₃ , CH ₄ N ₂ O
Fremstad and others, 2005	7	Norway	Shrubland		x	2.45	1	1	7/35/70	108	NH ₄ NO ₃
Gordon and others, 2001	8	Svalbard	Shrubland		x	0.34	1	1	10/50	85	NH ₄ NO ₃
Gough and Hobbie, 2003	9	Alaska	Shrubland		x	0.25	1	1	100	36	NH ₄ NO ₃
Gough and others, 2002	10	Alaska	Shrubland		x	0.25	1	1	100	108	NH ₄ NO ₃
Helsper and others, 1983	11	Netherlands	Shrubland		x	35.31	1	1	86	72	NH ₄ NO ₃
Hogan and others, 2010	12	Scotland	Shrubland	4, 6 ^b		12.29	1	1	8/24/56	41	NH ₄ Cl, NaNO ₃ , NH ₄ Cl + NaNO ₃
Jacobson and Gustafsson, 2001	13	Sweden	Forest		x	7.75	1	1	150	60	NH ₄ NO ₃
Johansson and others 2012	14	Sweden	Forest		x	1.48	2	1	6/12.5/25/50	48	NH ₄ NO ₃
Kelley and Epstein, 2009	15	Alaska	Grassland		x	0.25	1	1	100	24	NH ₄ NO ₃
Kellner, 1993	16	Sweden	Forest		x	2.71	1	1	120/240/360/600	180	NH ₄ NO ₃

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Lee and Caporn, 1998	17	Wales	Shrubland		x	12.29	1	1	4/8/12/20	72	NH ₄ NO ₃
Nilsson and others, 2002	18	Sweden	Shrubland		x	1.48	1	1	50	112	NH ₄ H ₂ PO ₄ , KNO ₃ , NH ₄ NO ₃ + NO ₃
Nybakken and others, 2009	19	Sweden	Forest	2, 3	x	1.48	2	1	50	3	NH ₄ NO ₃
Ochoa-Hueso and Manrique (2011)	20	Spain	Shrubland	1, 2	x	9.71	1	1	10/20/50	54	NH ₄ NO ₃
Ochoa-Hueso and others (2013)	21	Spain	Shrubland	4, 5, 6 ^e		9.71	1	1	10/20/50	54	NH ₄ NO ₃
Ochoa-Hueso and others (2017)	22	Spain	Shrubland		x	9.71	1	1	10/20/50	54	NH ₄ NO ₃
Olsson and Kellner, 2006	23	Sweden	Forest		x	2.00	1	1	120/240/360/480/600	180	NH ₄ NO ₃
Palmqvist and Dahlman, 2006	24	Sweden	Forest, Grassland	2, 4 ^d		1.84	2	1	25/150/300	4	(NH ₄)SO ₄ , KNO ₃ , C ₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃
Pilkington and others, 2007	25	Wales	Shrubland		x	12.29	1	1	10/20	48	NH ₄ NO ₃
Power and others, 2006	26	England	Shrubland		x	12.95	1	1	7.7/15.4	108	(NH ₄)SO ₄
Sheppard and others, 2011	27	Scotland	Shrubland		x	12.29	1	1	8/24/56	84	NH ₄ Cl
Skrindo and Øland, 2002	28	Norway	Forest		x	5.00	1	1	30/90	72	NH ₄ NO ₃
Soudzilovskaia and others, 2005	29	Russia	Grassland		x	7.74	1	1	90	39	CH ₄ N ₂ O
Sparrius and others, 2013	30	Netherlands	Grassland		x	35.31	1	1	7.2	32	NH ₄ NO ₃
Sundberg and others, 2001	31	Sweden	Forest	1, 2, 4, 7 ^a		1.84	1	2	9	4	NH ₄ NO ₃
Taboada and others, 2018	32	Spain	Shrubland		x	4.43	1	1	10/20/50/56	108	NH ₄ NO ₃
Vagts and Kinder 1999	33	Germany	Shrubland	4, 5 ^e	x	10.26	1	1	150	24	NH ₄ NO ₃
Tomassen and others, 2004	34	Ireland	Shrubland		x	5.57	1	1	20/40/80	39	NH ₄ N ₂ O ₃ + (NH ₄)SO ₄
Van den Elzen and others, 2018	35	Scotland	Shrubland	4 ^b		12.29	1	1	24	132	NH ₄ Cl, NaNO ₃
Wang and others, 2018	36	China	Forest	4, 5, 6 ^f		23.26	1	2	6.25/12.5/25/50	7	NH ₄ NO ₃

Wang and others, 2019	37	China	Forest		x	23.26	1	2	6.25/12.5/25/50	7	NH ₄ NO ₃
Wardle and others, 2013	38	Sweden	Shrubland		x	1.48	1	1	50	132	NH ₄ H ₂ PO ₄ , KNO ₃ , NH ₄ NO ₃
Zhou and others, 2016	39	China	Desert	1, 2, 5, 6 ^g		3.90	1	2	3/5/10/15/30	41	NH ₄ NO ₃ + NH ₄ Cl

Metabolism: publications with data on metabolic responses: 1, photosynthesis; 2, pigments; 3, secondary metabolites; 4, thallus N; 5, nutrient content; 6, enzymatic activity; 7, fungal biomass. Abundance: publications with abundance response data: x, available data. * Data from Dentener *et al.* (2006). Ecotype: 1, terricolous; 2, epiphyte. Symbiosis: 1, chlorolichen; 2, cyanolichen. Superscript letters for studies on metabolism refer to citations that justify the use of thallus N as a metabolic variable: ^aDahlman and others, 2002, ^bSheppard and others, 2011, ^cOchoa-Hueso and others (2017), ^dJohansson and others 2012, ^eVagts and Kinder 1999, ^fWang and others, 2019, ^gZhou and others, 2016.

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4 643 **Figure 1.** World map representing the global total N deposition (kg N/ha/year) for the year 1993 according to the model of Dentener and others (2006). The red
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6 644 dots represent the 31 experimental sites considered in the publications.
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646 **Figure 2.** Effects of experimental fertilization with N (lnRR) on the abundance (a) and metabolism (b) of lichens based on a series of environmental variables,
647 procedural variables and lichen traits. The points with the error bars indicate the mean effect size and 95% confidence interval. The numbers in parentheses
648 correspond to the number of observations. Error bars that do not cross the zero line indicate significant differences associated with the addition of N ($p < 0.05$),
649 as compared to the control (no N added).

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651 **Figure 3.**Structural equation models related to the response of lichens to N in terms of abundance (a-c) and metabolism (d-f). Non-significant p-

652 values of the Fisher’s C statistic indicate good fit of the models. The arrows indicate predicted relationships between variables. The thickness is proportional to

653 the size of the effect. †p <0.1, *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001. Gray arrows indicate nonsignificant relationships but tested as part of the a priori models

654 (described in the main text). Arrows pointing to other arrows denote interaction terms included in the model. Relationships in 1. and 2. indicate correlated error

655 terms of two variables but do not imply causality. R^2_{mar} = percentage of variance (marginal R^2) explained by the model. d.f. = degrees of freedom.

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3 658 **Figure 4.** Partial correlation plots for significant relationships found in the abundance SEM
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5 659 from Fig. 3a. In panel c, white dots and solid line indicate relationships at low background
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7 660 N deposition sites ($< 10 \text{ kg N ha yr}^{-1}$), while black dots and dashed line indicate
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9 661 relationships at high background N deposition sites ($> 10 \text{ kg N ha yr}^{-1}$). In panel d, white
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11 662 dots and solid line indicate relationships at low isothermality sites (< 25), while black
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13 663 dots and dashed line indicate relationships at high isothermality sites (> 25).
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665 **Figure 5.** Partial correlation plots for significant relationships found in the metabolism SEM
 666 from Figure 3d.

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3 669 **Supplementary Table 1.** Spearman rank correlations between environmental and
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5 670 procedural variables and the *lnRR* of abundance-related metrics. [Please, see attached .csv
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7 671 file].
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13 673 **Supplementary Table 1.** Spearman rank correlations between environmental and
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15 674 procedural variables and the *lnRR* of metabolism-related metrics. [Please, see attached
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17 675 .csv file].
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